

Welcome to the 2nd Newsletter of the DIGITISE project!

As we mark an important stage in the DIGITISE project, this edition offers a closer look at the work being carried out across the consortium through the 1st year of the project duration. In this issue, you'll find a feature **article and video summary from our recent 3rd Plenary Meeting in Caparica**, where partners gathered to assess progress and refine plans for the next phase.

We also bring you updates from the project's **Work Packages and demonstration sites, highlighting how digital and cross-sector solutions** supporting the energy transition. Additionally, we've included a series of interviews with partners, offering insight into their roles within DIGITISE, the technologies they are contributing, and how these innovations may benefit citizens and drive digital transformation in the energy sector.

We thank you for your continued interest in DIGITISE and wish you a pleasant and restful holiday period.

DIGITISE Team

DIGITISE Project Holds 3rd Plenary Meeting Summing Up the 1st Year of the Progress

The DIGITISE project team convened for its 3rd Plenary Meeting in the scenic setting of the Lisbon shoreline, marking an important milestone in the project's development. Hosted by Unparallel Innovation, the meeting brought together partners from across Europe to assess progress during the 1st of the project, align on technical goals, and chart a clear path forward for the next phase of the initiative.

[**Read the full article**](#)

Watch the recap!

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#DIGITISEdemos

Dimitrios Fotis

DIGITISE WP6 Leader
EU Project Coordinator
METLEN

It's about how we apply technology to create an inclusive and sustainable energy ecosystem!

As part of our #DIGITISEReam campaign, we are delighted to introduce Dimitrios Fotis, EU Project Coordinator at METLEN. Dimitrios manages METLEN's contributions to the DIGITISE project, leveraging his expertise in economics and business strategy to foster innovation and drive sustainability in the energy sector.

[**Read the full interview**](#)

Digital tools for consumers, demand-side flexibility, and efficient energy system by Arden Energy

The Irish demonstration site focuses on the Ringsend Sustainable Energy Community, a proactive local partner working to raise awareness and engage the community on energy use, efficiency, and sustainability. Their role is central to consumer empowerment, supporting local understanding and participation in clean energy transitions.

[**Read the full interview**](#)

Melani Furlan

DIGITISE Demo Leader
Community Energy | Solar Design Engineer
ZEZ

Citizen Energy in Croatia: An Interview with Melani Furlan (ZEZ) on Community-Driven Innovation in DIGITISE

In this interview we are talking with Melani Furlan, a Community Energy and Solar Design Engineer at ZEZ, to learn more about the Croatian demonstration site for the DIGITISE project.

[Read the full interview](#)

ESPINARDO - A Spanish Demonstration Site for the DIGITISE Project

The DIGITISE project supports the energy transition by creating digital tools to help consumers make informed choices. A key demonstration site is Espinardo in Murcia, Spain, where energy flexibility and efficiency solutions are tested. This article outlines the site's goals, technologies, and the challenges of integrating digital solutions into Spain's energy system.

[Read the full interview](#)

#DIGITISEwps

Bridging Differences for a Unified Goal – Interview with Boniface Dominick Mselle, WP2 Leader

We had the pleasure of speaking with Boniface Dominick Mselle, an R&D+I Energy Engineer at CIRCE, a leading research and training centre focused on technology transfer and sustainability. With a PhD in industrial engineering and

IT and over eight years of experience in energy systems, Boniface is dedicated to bridging the gap between research and real-world applications in Work Package 2 of DIGITISE project.

[Read the full interview](#)

Empowering Energy Consumers through Digital Intelligence - Work Package 5 (WP5) in the DIGITISE Project

The DIGITISE project's Work Package 5 (WP5), led by UBITECH, is dedicated to developing digital solutions that empower consumers and prosumers in the evolving energy landscape. At its core, WP5 leverages the DIGITISE Household Digital Twin and a suite of applications to enhance energy literacy, support informed decisions, and facilitate efficient energy usage.

[Read the full interview](#)

DIGITISE impact through Communication, Dissemination, Stakeholder Engagement, and Business Innovation

DIGITISE impact through Communication, Dissemination, Stakeholder Engagement, and Business Innovation

WP7 is the Workpackage in charge of the project's communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement and business innovation. Led by AUSTRALO, with Mission Publiques responsible for the Stakeholders Engagement, Ubitech overseeing Exploitation and Business Innovation, and MIW Energia leading the tasks related to Replication and Scale Up.

[Read the full article](#)

Smart Applications for Smarter Energy Use in DIGITISE

In the DIGITISE project, Work Package 4 (WP4) led by University College Dublin, is dedicated to delivering practical, AI-driven tools that help

Scalability is not just as a technical hurdle, but as a multi-dimensional challenge that requires

Bringing Citizens into the Energy Conversation - An Interview with Benoît Verhulst of

prosumers understand and manage their energy use more effectively. With direct connections to the data and analytics developed in other Work Packages, WP4 plays a crucial role in bringing the DIGITISE ecosystem to life.

[Go to the article](#)

alignment of technology

As part of the DIGITISE initiative, AppArt is helping to develop a smart energy systems by combining deep technical expertise with a human-centred approach. With a strong background in EU-funded R&D and a focus on AI, IoT, and digital infrastructure, the AppArt team brings valuable insight to the project's mission of empowering consumers in the energy transition.

[Go to article](#)

Missions Publiques

In this interview, Benoît Verhulst, Participatory Process Manager at Missions Publiques, shares how his team is supporting the DIGITISE project through inclusive, deliberative engagement. With experience across local and international initiatives, Benoît explains the importance of high-quality dialogue, long-term community involvement, and linking digital innovation with real-life needs.

[Go to article](#)

#DIGITISEyearTWO

In its second year, the DIGITISE project will focus on meeting its M18 milestone, due in six months. Key activities include technical integration planning, coordinating the first phase of pilot activities, and addressing identified dependencies and equipment needs. The project will also continue collaboration with sister projects (DECODIT, ENERGENIUS, EU-DREAM, and CELINE) through joint efforts such as a white paper, webinars, podcasts, and participation

in ENLIT Europe 2025 (18–20 November, Bilbao). This collaboration aims to empower consumers by making energy information more accessible and encouraging active involvement in the energy transition.

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